

A mild and efficient method for the deoxygenation of α,β -epoxyketones to enones[†]

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Manuscript received 13 August 1999

A mild and efficient method for the deoxygenation of α,β -epoxyketones to the corresponding enones in excellent yield has been developed using a titanium(III) radical initiator. The deoxygenation occurred with complete loss of stereochemistry in the products.

Blocking and deblocking of functional groups are of great significance in organic chemistry specially, during the total synthesis of complex natural products. Deoxygenation of epoxides is a valuable transformation which can be achieved in one or more steps with complete retention or inversion¹. Although there are several methodologies reported in the literature including extensive reviews² for such deoxygenations of epoxides, a very few reagents are known to be useful for the deoxygenation of α,β -epoxyketones to the corresponding enones³. But most of them are involved in costly reagents or multistep and drastic procedures. So a better method of epoxide deoxygenation is still desired.

We report here a mild and efficient procedure for the deoxygenation of α,β -epoxyketones to enones using a titanium(III) species as a radical source⁴. Titanium(III) chloride (Cp_2TiCl) was prepared *in situ* from commercially available titanocene dichloride (Cp_2TiCl_2) and Zn-dust in THF and was used for the purpose. Although deoxygenation of simple epoxides have been successfully achieved⁴ by using this reagent, deoxygenation of α,β -epoxyketones to enones is still unexplored. Thus, a series of α,β -epoxyketones prepared by standard procedures⁵ were subjected to deoxygenation⁶ using Cp_2TiCl in THF at room temperature to afford the corresponding enones in excellent yield. The results are summarized in Table 1. Cyclic and acyclic β,β -disubstituted, β -monosubstituted and β -unsubstituted epoxyketones underwent smooth deoxygenation to furnish the corresponding enones in excellent yields. The deoxygenation of acyclic epoxides with different β -substituents (entry 9 and 10, Table 1) occurred with complete loss of stereochemistry in the products. Thus, deoxygenation of the *cis*-epoxyketones afforded the *trans*-enones as the sole product. The complete loss of stereochemistry in these systems suggests the intervention of a long-lived intermediate. Probably, the deoxygenation proceeds in discrete one-electron steps via a radical intermediate as shown in eq. 1.

In conclusion, we have demonstrated a mild and efficient methodology for the deoxygenation of α,β -epoxyketones to enones in excellent yield using Cp_2TiCl prepared *in situ* from Cp_2TiCl_2 with Zn-dust in THF.

Table 1. Deoxygenation of α,β -epoxyketones by Cp_2TiCl in THF

Entry	Substrate	Product	Yield (%) ^a
1			90
2			96
3			90
4			95
5			96
6			90
7			85
8			86

[†]Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

Table-1 (contd.)

9		91 ^b	
10		85 ^b	
11		90	
12		89	
13		85	

^aYields refer to chromatographically pure isolated products.

^bDeoxygenation occurred with total loss of stereochemistry in the products.

Experimental

Epoxides were prepared by the standard procedure⁵ from the easily accessible⁶ enones and were compared with the authentic samples⁶. The products were purified by column chromatography over silica gel (60–120 mesh) using ethyl acetate and petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) as the eluent and were compared with the authentic samples^{5,6}. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on a 300 MHz NMR spectrometer. Tetrahydrofuran was distilled over sodium.

General procedure for deoxygenation : A solution of Cp₂TiCl₂ (3 mmol) in dry THF (20 ml) was stirred with Zn-dust (12 mmol) under an argon atmosphere at room temperature for 1 h. The resulting green solution was then transferred to a three-necked flask through a cannula. To this solution was added dropwise a solution of the epoxide (1.3 mmol) in THF (5 ml) and the resulting mixture was stirred for 45 min. The reaction mixture was then quenched with a saturated aqueous solution of NaH₂PO₄ (10 ml). After 10 min, water (20 ml) was added to it and extracted with Et₂O (4 × 25 ml). The ether extract was washed with brine (10

ml) and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue obtained was chromatographed over silica gel (ethyl acetate-petroleum ether) to afford the enone.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Department of Science & Technology, Government of India, for financial assistance.

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